

Using CRISPR/Cas9 to investigate the developmental roles of *Plastin* in *Ciona*, Part 1: testing its role in papilla cell elongation

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Introduction

While our research group is currently collaborating with Arcadia Science on knocking out three genes identified by the Zoogole platform as human monogenic disease model candidates in the tunicate *Ciona robusta* [1], we were inspired by a parallel collaboration between Arcadia and David Booth's group at UCSF [2]. Zoogole identified the gene *Plastin 1* (*PLS1*) as an exceptional candidate to study in the choanoflagellate *Salpingoeca rosetta* based on predicted structural similarity. This gene encodes an actin-bundling protein, and associated mutations are implicated in hearing loss in humans, likely through effects on mechanosensitive hair cell developmental defects [3, 4].

In *Ciona*, we previously identified a *PLS1* homolog (KH gene ID KH.S521.5, KY21 gene ID KY21.Chr1.1966) as being upregulated in the developing sensory-adhesive papillae of the larva (**Figure 1**) [5], which is a set of three protruding clusters of cells that are elongated along the apical-basal axis [6]. Of note, we found that this gene (which we call herein *Plastin*) is upregulated by the transcription factor *Islet*, which is crucial for the elongated cell morphology of the papillae [5, 7]. We therefore had previously hypothesized that *Ciona* *Plastin* might be important for regulating actin dynamics during papilla cell elongation.

***Plastin in situ* hybridization**

Figure 1. Whole-mount, fluorescent mRNA *in situ* hybridization for *Plastin* in *Ciona robusta* embryos, revealing strong expression in the developing papilla region (arrowheads). Expression can also be seen in the endoderm of the head/trunk and tail (endodermal strand), especially at mid-tailbud stage.

Zoogole did not suggest *Ciona* *Plastin* as a particularly close structural match for human *Plastin 1*, coming in at a very middling portfolio rank of 29 (out of 50). However, we noticed that the particular Uniprot sequence of *Ciona* *Plastin* used by Zoogole came from an ENSEMBL gene model that is incomplete, missing a substantial portion of the exons encoding the conserved C-terminus (**Figure 2**). We we therefore curious whether, in reality, *Ciona* *Plastin* might have

scored higher and could serve as a good model for studying conserved Plastin functions. Here we describe our first attempt to knock out *Plastin* in the papillae of the *Ciona* larva to potentially reveal resulting defects in cell elongation.

Figure 2. A) Diagram of KY21 (top, blue) and ENSEMBL (bottom, orange) gene models, showing that the ENSEMBL model is likely incomplete. B) Diagram comparing the predicted domain structures of the KY21 Plastin protein sequence (top) and the UniProt sequence (bottom, based on the ENSEMBL gene model). The third Calponin Homology (CH) domain is truncated, and the fourth CH domain is missing, in the UniProt sequence. EFh = EF-hand, calcium-binding motif. Protein domains analyzed by SMART [8].

Methods and results

Several single-chain guide RNAs (sgRNAs) targeting *Plastin* were designed and validated by Illumina-based amplicon sequencing followed our established routine protocol [9], available at protocols.io (dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.14egnr97yl5d/v1). Of these, we selected the sgRNAs shown in **Table 1** for use in combination to knock out *Plastin* by tissue-specific CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis. **Figure 3** shows the indel plots indicating successful targeting.

sgRNA	G(N19)	Efficacy
Plastin.2.31	GAACGGCTGCATCGAGAAGG	>40%
Plastin.6.18	GAATGGCAGACGCAGAGTTG	>30%

Table 1. *Plastin* sgRNAs used in this study.

Pls.2.31 sgRNA (exon 2)
GAACGGCTGCATCGAGAAGG

Pls.6.18 sgRNA (exon 6)
GAATGGCAGACGCAGAGTTG

Figure 3. Insertion/deletion (indel) plots generated by Azenta/GeneWiz’s “Amplicon-EZ” illumina sequencing service. Black arrows indicate indels generated by CRISPR/Cas9 using the indicated sgRNAs. Red asterisks indicate naturally-occurring indels.

Tissue-specific CRISPR was carried out as previously detailed, using the *Foxc* promoter to drive expression of Cas9::GemininN-terminus (a more efficient form of Cas9 for CRISPR experiments in *Ciona*) in the papilla lineage [5, 10]. Embryos were co-electroporated with *Foxc>H2B::mCherry* reporter plasmid to label the cell nuclei of the CRISPR’d lineage, as well as a *CryBG>Unc-76::GFP* reporter plasmid to label the cytoplasm of the axial columnar cells (ACCs), the central, most elongated cell type of the papillae [11, 12]. The electroporation recipes (per 700 µl of electroporation volume) were thus:

Plastin CRISPR

- 10 µg *Foxc>H2B::mCherry*
- 35 µg *CryBG>Unc-76::GFP*
- 35 µg *Foxc>Cas9::Geminin-Nter*
- 40 µg *U6>Plastin.2.31 sgRNA*
- 40 µg *U6>Plastin.6.18 sgRNA*

Negative control CRISPR

- 10 µg *Foxc>H2B::mCherry*
- 35 µg *CryBG>Unc-76::GFP*
- 35 µg *Foxc>Cas9::Geminin-Nter*
- 80 µg *U6>Control sgRNA*

Larvae were fixed at 17 hpf (20°C) and imaged using a Leica DMI8 inverted epifluorescence microscope. Raw images can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17892564>. ACC lengths were measured along the apical-basal axis using LASX software, following the previously established method [5]. Raw lengths were plotted and analyzed in GraphPad Prism.

We observed that ACC length was not significantly reduced upon *Plastin* CRISPR in the papilla lineage (**Figure 2**). This was not entirely surprising, as previous monogenic knockouts of other genes encoding cytoskeletal regulators downstream of *Islet* (e.g. *Villin*, *Tubulin alpha*) failed to result in significant, consistent shortening of the papillae [5]. This in spite of *Islet* knockouts or dominant-negatives showing significantly shortened papillae [5, 7].

Figure 4. A) Images of the papillae in 17 hpf (20°C) larvae, comparing the negative control CRISPR and *Plastin* CRISPR conditions. Yellow arrow indicates axial columnar cell (ACC) length along their apical-basal axis, which was measured for this assay. Larvae counterstained with DAPI (white overlay). B) Quantification of ACC cell lengths, showing a slight but not statistically significant drop in average length upon tissue-specific *Plastin* CRISPR knockout. ns = not statistically significant, Welch's t-test (two-tailed).

We hypothesize that multiple genes downstream of *Islet* may be acting in a partially overlapping or redundant manner to regulate the cytoskeleton during papilla cell elongation. For instance, *Villin* (KY21.Chr9.368) encodes another actin-bundling protein and therefore might be compensating for loss of *Plastin*. In fact, *Villin* is expressed later, specifically in elongating central *Islet*⁺ cells that give rise to the ACCs [5]. The expression of *Plastin* during tailbud stages throughout the entire papilla territory (**Figure 1**) suggests it may be important for the earlier thickening of the papilla epithelium. Thus, it is possible that *Villin* and *Plastin* may combine in partially overlapping ways to carry out different steps in papilla morphogenesis. In mammals, a triple knockout of actin-bundling factors (*Villin*, *Plastin1*, and *Epsin*) reduced intestinal microvilli length but did not prevent their formation [13].

With this in mind, our next goal is to perform the first tissue-specific, double CRISPR knockouts in the papillae of *Ciona*. More specifically, we plan to target both *Villin* and *Plastin* for CRISPR-mediated mutagenesis in the same individuals. Our results with the double *Plastin/Villin* CRISPR (whether negative or positive) will be reported in the second installment of this project.

Supplemental sequences

Validation primer (forward) for *Plastin.2.31*: ATAAAGTGTCACAAGATAGGACATC
 Validation primer (reverse) for *Plastin.2.31*: GTATTACCCGGGCAAATTC
 Validation primer (forward) for *Plastin.6.18*: ATGTAAGCAAATCGTGAAAAGGT
 Validation primer (reverse) for *Plastin.6.18*: ATTTATACCTGGGTTGTGAATC

>Plastin *in situ* hybridization probe template sequence

ATGGCAAATGATGAATATGAATCCGGAATCAGACAAGCATTGGCAAATATGTCACTTGGAACAGATGATG
TGGATACTGTTGTTAATGCATTTATAACTGTTGACACCAACCAGAACGGCTGCATCGAGAAGGAGGAAGT
AGAAGACTTGTTTAGAGAGTCGGGTTTAAACTTCCAAAGTATAAGATCCGTGATTTAATGAAGGAAGCT
GATTTGGATCGAAACAATACCATCAGCCCAACAGAATTTGCCCGGATCTACGCCCAGCTGACATCTGAAG
AATATTCCCCTCAATTTAAACTGCAATCACTACAAAAGTCAAACCTGAAAAAATCAGAAATATCCAATGC
GTCTGCTGAAGGGACTCAACATTCTTATTCGGAAGAAGAATGTGCTGCGTTCAACAAATGGATCACAAAG
AATTTGAAAGACGATGATGATTGTAAAGATCGAGTGAAGAACATGCAAGCTAACGATTTCTTTAAACGGA
TGAAAGATGGAATTATCTATGTAAGATGGTAAATCTTTCCCAACCAGACACCATTGATGAGAGAACAAT
AAATAAGAAAAACCTTAACATTTATCGAGAACAGGAAAATATCAATCTTGCCCTCAACTCTGCGTCTGCC
ATTGGATGCAACATTGTGAACATAGGAGCCGAGGATATTGTTCAAAGAAAGAGCATCTCATCTCGGTC
TTTTATGGCAAGTCATCAGAATCGGACTTTTCAGAAAGATCGATTTGATTACAAACCAGGTATTAGTGC
TCTTCTGTTAGAAGGTGAAACATTGGATGACCTTAGGGCAATGTCACCTGAAGATCTCCTTTTAAAGGTGG
ATGAATTATCATCTTCAACAATCTGACAAATACAAAGAGGCAACTGGAGGAAAAGTTATCACAAACTTCA
GCGCAGACATTAAGGACTCCATTGCTTACACTTGTCTATTGGAGAGAATCCAACCAATTGATGAAGAGAC
ACAACAATATGAACTGTCTCCACCAATTTGTGCCAAAATTGAAGCAAATCCAACACTGCCAGAGCTGAA
TCCATGCTTGAAGATGCCGAGCGAATGAATTGCCGAGAGTTTGTGACCGCTAAAGACATTACCAAAGGAA
ATGCTAAACTCAACATGGCTTTTCGTGGCAAACCTATTCAACACACACCCTGCCCTTACACCAAGAGACAT
GGAAGAGATAGAAGAGGAAAAGAGAGAAGTGAAGACATATAGAAACTGGATGAACAGTTTGGGAGTTTCT
CCTCGTGTCAACAAGTTCACCAGAGACTTAACTTCTGGACTTGTCTGTTTCAACTATACGAGCAAGTTA
AGCCAGGTTGCGTGGATTGGTCCAAGGTTGATAAAAAGTGCAAAGGAAGATTCAAAAAACT

>KY21 gene model protein sequence missing in ENSEMBL/UniProt model

MANDEYESGIRQALANMSLGTDDVDTVVNAFITVDTNQNCGIEKEEVEDLFRESGLKLPKYKIRDLMKEA
DLDRNNTISPTEFARIYAQLTSEEYSRQFKTAITTKSNLKKSEISNASAEGTQHSYSEEECAAFNKWITK
NLKDDDDCKDRVKNMQANDFFKRMKDGIILCKMVNLSQPDTIDERTINKKNLNIYREQENINLALNSASA
IGCNIVNIGAEDIVQKKEHLILGLLWQVIRIGLFRKIDLIHNPGISALLLEGETLDDLRAMSPEDLLLRW
MNYHLQQSDKYKEATGGKVIITNFSADIKDSIAYTCLLERIQPIDEETQQYELSPPICAKIEAKSNTARAE
SMLEDAERMNCREFVTAKDITKGNAKLNMAFVANLFNTHPALTPRDMEIEIEEKREVKTYRNWMNSLGV
PRVKNFTRDLTSLGLVLFQLYEQVKPGCVDWSKVDKKCKGRFQKLQNLQYAVEVAKQLGFVIVGIEGNDIL
AENETLVLAVVWQIMRAYTFKILETLSEDGKPVKEQIIVDWNQKLSDSGKETQISSFKDSEIKKSLVVI
DLIDAIVPGSIRYEVVTAGETEEDQYSNAKYAVSMARKIGARIYALPDDLVEGKAKMVATIFACL MGRGM
KEVE

>ENSEMBL/UniProt gene model protein sequence

MANDEYESGIRQALANMSLGTDDVDTVVNAFITVDTNQNCGIEKEEVEDLFRESGLKLPKYKIRDLMKEA
DLDRNNTISPTEFARIYAQLTSEEYSRQFKTAITTKSNLKKSEISNASAEGTQHSYSEEECAAFNKWITK
NLKDDDDCKDRVKNMQANDFFKRMKDGIILCKMVNLSQPDTIDERTINKKNLNIYREQENINLALNSASA
IGCNIVNIGAEDIVQKKEHLILGLLWQVIRIGLFRKIDLILEPGISALLLEGETLDDLRAMSPEDLLLRW
MNYHLQQSDKYKEATGGKVIITNFSADIKDSIAYTCLLERIQPIDEETQQYELSPPICAKIEAKSNTARAE
SMLEDAERMNCREFVTAKDITKGNAKLNMAFVANLFNTHPALTPRDMEIEIEDSKLSPPTTEEKREVKTYRN
WMNSLGVSPRVKNFTRDLTSLGLVLFQLYEQVKPGCVDWSKVDK

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